

Reaction Between an Ethanolic Solution Containing the Anion $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$ and Gaseous Sulphur Dioxide

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The kinetics of the reaction between $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$ and SO_2 was followed spectrophotometrically at 390 nm and a temperature study to determine activation parameters was carried out. The observed rate constants were calculated from the initial slopes and the reaction was found to be first order with respect to each of the reactants. Infrared spectral data suggest the presence of Rh-S and S-C bonds in the product and a shift in one of the CO bands was observed. These observations, in conjunction with the high negative entropy of activation (-64.6eu), suggest that SO_2 is inserted between Rh and CO. The data were found to obey a rate equation analogous to the Michaelis-Menten equation employed in the analysis of enzyme kinetic data.

THE complex ion $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$ is prepared by refluxing an ethanolic solution of rhodium trichloride with carbon monoxide giving a yellow coloured solution¹. When sulphur dioxide is subsequently passed through this solution, the colour changes to orange. Infrared evidence obtained in this work suggest that SO_2 is inserted between the metal and CO. It is of interest to note that if the orange solution is concentrated the resulting solid is the dark red complex¹ $[\text{Rh}(\text{SO}_2)\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$. Infrared measurements¹ confirm the absence of CO in this solid complex.

In recent years a great deal of interest has been given to insertion reactions involving transition metal complexes. Insertion reactions occur frequently in the general area of catalysis, particularly in the reversible oxygenation of metal complexes involving synthetic oxygen carrying systems. These studies initially dealt with group VIII square planar complexes with particular emphasis on the type and degree of the metal-ligand bond. Later, however, they were broadened to include carbon monoxide, sulphur dioxide and ethylene metal complexes.*

Attention was heretofore focused on synthetic aspects and few kinetic studies were undertaken². This has been true in the case of sulphur dioxide insertion reactions as well. Following the discovery of these insertion reactions³ attention has been entirely focused on synthetic aspects⁴ and it was not until recently^{5,6} that kinetic considerations were attended to.

This paper deals with the kinetics and mechanism of the reaction between sulphur dioxide and $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$ in absolute ethanol.

Experimental

Materials : All chemicals used were of reagent grade unless otherwise specified. Rhodium trichloride was purchased from Johnson Matthey Chemicals Ltd., London. Liquified sulphur dioxide was purchased from BDH Chemicals Ltd., London. Carbon monoxide was generated by reacting formic acid with sulphuric acid.

Preliminary procedure : The complex ion $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$ was prepared¹⁰ by passing carbon monoxide through an ethanolic solution of rhodium trichloride (0.20 g in 30ml ethanol). The solution was refluxed for five hours with continuous stirring. During this time the color of the solution slowly changed from dark red to pale yellow. The infrared spectrum of the resulting solution indicated the presence of CO stretching bands at 2010 and 2080 cm^{-1} .

The concentrations of sulphur dioxide in ethanolic solutions were determined by iodometry.

Kinetics : The reaction between sulphur dioxide and $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$ was followed at 390 nm on a Unicam SP 8000 spectrophotometer in the temperature range, $15-30 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The reagent solutions were thermostated separately for at least 20 min. before the reaction was initiated by rapid mixing.

The order of the reaction with respect of sulphur dioxide and $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$ was determined from the initial rates by varying the concentration of one species while holding the other constant. The rate constants were calculated from the initial rates.

* Reference 1 and references cited therein.

Infrared measurements were carried out on ethanolic solutions containing the insertion complex using a Perkin Elmer 257 grating spectrophotometer.

Results

1. *Kinetic Measurements* : Plots of initial rate of change of absorbance for various solutions containing equimolar concentrations of $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$ ($6.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) and varying concentrations of sulphur dioxide (0.024–1.162M) were found to be linear and passing through the origins. The reference path had two cells in tandem, one containing sulphur dioxide and the other the complex ion. The sample path also had two cells in tandem, one cell containing the complex ion and sulphur dioxide, both of the same initial concentration as in the reference path, and the other cell containing pure solvent. Thus, at the time of initiation of the reaction the absorbance reading was zero.

TABLE 1 (a)—DEPENDENCE OF THE OBSERVED RATE CONSTANT, k_{obs} , ON (SO_2) . $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^- = 6.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. SOLVENT: ETHANOL. TEMP. = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$.

(SO_2) M	$k_{obs} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
0.024	1.30
0.032	2.00
0.042	2.32
0.092	4.35
0.120	5.80
0.475	14.27
1.162	20.60

The dependence of the observed rate constant, k_{obs} , on the concentration of sulphur dioxide is given in Table 1 (a).

The order of the reaction with respect to the complex ion was determined by varying the concentration of the complex ion in the range $(1.8-27) \times 10^{-4} M$ with a fixed sulphur dioxide concentration of 0.03M.

TABLE 1 (b)—DEPENDENCE OF THE OBSERVED RATE CONSTANT k_{obs} ON THE CONCENTRATION OF $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$. $(\text{SO}_2) = 0.03 M$. SOLVENT: ETHANOL. TEMP. = $25 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$.

$[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^- \times 10^4 M$	$k_{obs} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
1.8	0.94
6.0	1.90
9.0	3.00
12.0	3.60
27.0	5.20

From Table 1(b) it is clear that the order with respect to the complex ion is unity.

A plot of k_{obs} against sulphur dioxide concentration is shown in Fig. 1. It is evident from this figure that the reaction is first order with respect to sulphur dioxide at low SO_2 concentrations and zero order at high concentrations.

Fig. 1

The dependence of k_{obs} on sulphur dioxide concentration is in agreement with the following rate expression :

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1 k_2 (\text{SO}_2)}{k_{-1} + k_2 (\text{SO}_2)} \quad \dots (1)$$

where k_1 and k_{-1} are the rate constants for the forward and reverse steps, respectively, in the process leading to the formation of the activated species, and k_2 is the rate for the decomposition of the activated species. k_{-2} does not appear in the above rate expression because the reaction essentially proceeds to completion.

Equation (1) may be rearranged as follows :

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{K_{-1}}{k_1 k_2} \frac{1}{(\text{SO}_2)} + \frac{1}{k_2} \quad \dots (2)$$

Fig. 2 is a plot of $\frac{1}{k_{obs}}$ against the reciprocal of the sulphur dioxide concentration. The linearity of this plot confirms the validity of the rate expression as given in equations (1) and (2). k_1 , as obtained from the intercept of Fig. 2 has the value of $28.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and the factor $\frac{k_{-1}}{k_1 k_2}$ as obtained from the slope has the value 16.86 min^{-1} . Thus $\frac{k_{-1}}{k_2} = 0.48$ and equation (1)

complex. It is probable that both of these factors are significant in this case although the precise contribution of each to ΔS^\ddagger cannot be ascertained. Sulphur dioxide is highly solvated in ethanol⁸ and the loss of the solvation shield upon binding to the complex ion is thus expected to increase the entropy of activation.

Further evidence for the proposed mechanism is furnished by infrared measurements carried out on the complex in solution (Table 4). The presence of S-C and Rh-S bonds in the product indicates the formation of an insertion product. The appearance of infrared bands at 700 cm^{-1} and 1610 cm^{-1} indicates the formation of an S-C bond, whereas the presence of a band at 1150 cm^{-1} strongly suggests the formation of an Rh-S bond. Furthermore, the presence of three broad bands at 1071 cm^{-1} , 910 cm^{-1} and 530 cm^{-1} is a strong indication for the appearance of $\text{SO}_2^{1,7}$.

The one-step mechanism

which is consistent with a very short-lived intermediate ($\tau=10^{-13}$ sec or less), may be excluded on the basis of experimental evidence from the literature and from this work. For example, Martín *et al*⁶, point out that such a single insertion step is normally associated with free radical reactions, a situation that clearly does not arise in this work. Secondly, the observation that the reaction rate does not continue to increase indefinitely as the ligand concentration is raised (Fig. 1) indicates that the mechanism is more complex than a simple bimolecular collision. The finding that the data could be fitted to equation 3 (as evidenced by Fig. 2), also serves to illustrate this point.

In addition to the above evidence, application of the continuous variation method to the reaction showed that the ratio¹¹ of complex to sulphur dioxide in the product is 1 : 1 (to be published). It is noteworthy that a further but extremely slow reaction takes place following the insertion of sulphur dioxide. In this reaction another sulphur dioxide molecule, as evidenced by the continuous variation method, reacts with the product to form a new complex¹¹ in which the ratio of complex to sulphur dioxide is 1 : 2.

Despite the large negative entropy of activation the reaction proceeds at a moderate rate because of the low ΔH^\ddagger value (5.8 Kcal/mole).

Analogy with Enzyme Kinetics : It may be noted that the present reaction is analogous to enzymatic reactions. In both cases an activated complex is formed from the reactants in a reversible process with rapid forward and back rates. This is followed by a slow step involving the breakdown of the activated complex into products.

Thus, the observed rate constant in enzymatic reactions as given by the Briggs and Haldane equation (4) is expected to behave in a similar way to k_{obs} in our reaction, upon varying the substrate concentration [analogous to (SO_2)].

In the equation,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_2}{1 + \frac{k_m}{(S)}} \quad \dots (4)$$

the Michaelis constant is given by $k_m = \frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1}$ and (S) is the substrate concentration. It is easily seen that substitution of $\frac{k_{-1} + k_2}{k_1}$ for k_m in equation(4) would yield a form identical to equation (1), in which SO_2 plays a similar role to the substrate S, at a fixed enzyme and complex ion concentrations, respectively.

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